

SASYA: Experimental Field Campaigns at Bardhaman Test Site

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Google Earth

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1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Agricultural resources are important dynamic natural resources and a major contributor to Indian economic growth. Accurate crop condition assessment, acreage estimation and on time yield assessment helps in providing a crucial information about the crops and leads to proper management of agricultural resources. In long term perspective, it is related to national and global food security. With large area synoptic coverage and timely measurements, remote sensing technology is able to fulfill all these requirements for crop related assessments. Remote sensing satellites are regularly used for crop acreage and production estimation, crop health monitoring. Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) capability to penetrate clouds and acquire data in all-weather condition makes it useful for monitoring and inventory purpose in Indian context. SAR signal can penetrate deeper into vegetation and give information about structure of leaves, stems and the background soil moisture content. The variation in SAR signal response due to crop structural properties and canopy moisture content from sowing to senescence stage is suitable for the utilization of microwave remote sensing for the crop type identification, growth monitoring and yield modeling.

1.2 Objective

The major focus of current research is : “Crop characterization using fully polarimetric RADARSAT-2 SAR data”. However, with the availability of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 at operation basis, leads towards a multi-sensor approach for crop monitoring. Thus the objectives are as follows:

- Crop classification and monitoring using multi-temporal polarimetric SAR data.
- Phenology estimation of geometrically different crops using polarimetric information content from quad-pol data
- Crop bio-physical parameter retrieval using multi-target inversion scheme from PolSAR data
- Combined analysis of SAR and optical data for plant traits

1.3 Experimental Plan

The proposed work involves acquisition of satellite imageries and in-synchronous crop related field measurements. As per the objectives of the project, analysis will be performed using fully polarimetric descriptors and polarimetric target decompositions. In addition we will try to use optical sensor data products for support.

- RADARSAT-2-C-band SAR Sensor (Quad-pol HH-VV-HV-VH) FQ Mode
- Sentinel-1 C-band SAR Sensor (Dual-pol VV-VH) IW Mode
- Sentinel-2 Optical Multi-spectral Sensor

1.4 Collaborative Network

SASYA: Field Experiment involved in several researchers from 03 different institutes of India, with around 10 people participating during the intensive measurements periods of the campaign. On the other hand, satellite datasets are acquired by the Canadian Space Agency (CSA) and European Space Agency (ESA) through Science and Operational Applications Research - Education International (SOAR-EI) Initiative programme¹ and Copernicus programme², respectively.

1.4.1 Ground Team

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¹SOAR-EI: <http://www.asc-csa.gc.ca/eng/funding-programs/funding-opportunities/ao/2017-soar-ei.asp>

²Copernicus policy: <https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/sentinel-data-access>

2. Discovering Test Site

2.1 Test Area

The present research is conducted over test site situated in the Damodar-Ajay river basin of East Bardhaman (Purba Bardhaman) district in the state of West Bengal, India as shown in Figure 2.1. It extends from $23^{\circ}18'39.43''\text{N}$, $87^{\circ}51'58.22''\text{E}$ to $23^{\circ}00'00.48''\text{N}$ and $88^{\circ}11'04.58''\text{E}$, with the site center coordinate of $23^{\circ}08'28.36''\text{N}$, $88^{\circ}01'22.89''\text{E}$.

Figure 2.1: Test site location (brown polygon) over LULC map of Purba Bardhaman, West Bengal.

The test area belongs to Old Alluvial Zone in terms of Agro-Climatic Zone (NARP), thus falls under sub-humid to humid eco-region. The test site covers an area of $25 \times 25 \text{ km}^2$ and is characterized by major annual crops viz. rice, potato, mustard, sesame and jute [1, 2]. The major crops are grown in two distinct seasons, monsoon or *kharif* (June-November) and winter or *rabi* (November-March). However, the present research is concentrated on the winter season crop Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*).

2.2 Soil Texture

The physiography of this area belongs to Alluvial plain with meander plain. The alluvial plain extends from the 80 m contour in west to 40 m contour in the east and formed of alluvium brought by the rivers Damodar and Ajoy and their tributaries. Successive floods and depositions gradually raised the area above flood level.

Figure 2.2: Soil texture variations over the test site.

For the test area, the soil data is available from the technical report by the Regional Centre (Kolkata) of the National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning¹. This database was published at a scale of 1:50000. The major soil textures present in the test site are Clay, Silty loam, Clayey sand as given in Fig. 2.2.

¹National Bureau of Soil Survey & Land Use Planning: http://14.139.123.73/bhoomigeoportal/publication_pdf/district_publication/Bardhaman.pdf

2.3 Crop cultivation practices

In this test site, the potato has a wide plantation calendar extending from November to December. In general, the potato is planted after harvesting of rice. Thus, delay in harvest of rice due to unexpected precipitation at its harvest period usually results in a late planting of potato than its optimum time for planting (Mid of November).

Due to the variability of the plantation period, adaptation of several potato plant varieties, e.g., Khufri Joyti, Kufri Chandramukhi, Kufri Pukhraj, etc. are likely planted in this area [3]. Amongst these varieties, Khurfi Chandramukhi has been reported as more affected by late blight diseases caused by *Phytophthora infestans* and primarily affects the potato production in this test site [4].

In general, potato is planted directly in the field in ridge and furrow system (Fig. 2.3). In this cultivation practices, a spacing of 45-60 cm between rows and 20 cm between plants is adopted. The total irrigation water requirement of potato varies between 350-550mm depending upon soil type and climate. Pre-Planting irrigation is advantageous for uniform germination of potato. Second irrigation is given after about a week and subsequent irrigations as and when required. However, irrigation is essential at critical stages in crop development, i.e., stolon formation, tuber initiation, and tuber development stage of the potato plant.

Figure 2.3: Ridge and furrow method of potato cultivation.

In addition, inter-cultural practices, such as hoeing and weeding followed by earthing up, are desirable when potato plants are about a month old. The first earthing-up is generally performed when the plants are ~15 to 25 cm high. The second earthing up is often done to cover up the tubers adequately. Harvesting of potatoes is done before the maximum soil temperature rises above 26 – 30°C during the end of February to avoid rotting of tubers due to high temperatures in March/April. The general practice is to stop the last irrigation before 10-15 days of harvesting of tubers, which allows tuber skin to become firm and tubers do not get bruised on harvesting [5].

- R** The potato plant and its underground tubers are affected by several diseases and pests. The important ones are late blight of potato, which affects the stems, leaves, and the tubers and causes heavy losses in tuber yield. Besides, leaf spot diseases such as early blight and leaf blotch and the diseases affecting tubers includes the blackscurf, common scab and wart.

3. Field measurement strategy

3.1 Sampling locations

In-situ measurements were collected intensively from December 2017 to March 2018 with several field campaigns. During the campaign, ~68 fields were selected for sampling. The nominal size of each field was ~60 m×60 m. Hand-held Trimble GPS instruments was used for finding the accurate location of ground truth points. Clustered sampling was used to collect the measurements from field as shown in Fig. 3.1. The sampling strategy planned by considering the JECAM SAR-Inter Comparison Experiment [6] and the Soil Moisture Active Passive Validation Experiment 2016 (SMAPVEX16-MB) [7, 8] protocols.

At each location, 5-6 fields were selected. In each field, sampling were done from two points. Vegetation and soil moisture were collected as following methods.

3.2 Soil moisture measurement

Surface soil moisture measurements will be acquired over selected agricultural fields coincident in time to flight overpasses. The hand held Delta Theta Probe will be used to measure soil moisture at near surface depths (5cm) at 2 locations in each field.

At each sample location, a total of 3 readings will be taken with the 1st reading at the top of a ridge, the 2nd reading in the middle of a ridge and the 3rd reading at the bottom of the depression between ridges. If there are no discernible ridges, all three readings will be taken and a note made on the sampling sheet that there were no ridges. Always insert the probe perpendicular to the soil surface as shown in the Fig. 3.2.

- Ⓡ Each sample location will avoid large cracks, dry clods or areas that have been heavily compacted by tractor wheels or foot traffic. Samplers must take care not to push the moisture probe in too far and cause compaction, especially if the soil is loose.

Figure 3.1: Test site with sampling locations. The cyan and light brown box defines the RADARSAT-2 and subset of Sentinel-2 coverage, respectively.

Figure 3.2: Probe locations in ridge-furrow system.

3.3 Vegetation sampling

The following vegetation properties will be measured for each sampling point (2 sampling point).

- VG1: Plant count
- VG2: Row spacing
- VG3: Row direction
- VG4: Plant Area Index (PAI)/LAI
- VG5: Biomass and canopy water content
- VG6: Plant height
- VG7: Phenology
- VG8: Leaf geometry (leaf inclination angle distribution, leaf geometry, leaf width, leaf thickness, leaf density, leaf layer height), stem parameters (stem geometry, stem length, stem radius, stem density, stem layer height) and ear parameters (ear/head geometry, ear length, ear radius, ear density, ear layer height). (Intensive campaigns)

3.3.1 VG1: Plant count

The density of plants will be determined by counting the number of emergent plants in a row along a fixed distance of 1 meter. This will be replicated for a total of 5 counts per sampling point by moving perpendicular to the rows. Counts will be recorded on data sheets and used with row spacing to calculate plant density.

3.3.2 VG2: Row spacing

Row spacing will be determined by measuring the distance between rows at each location where the plant counts are made. At each location, after the plant counts are made, the meter stick will be turned perpendicular to the row direction. At the soil level, the total distance will be measured between the centers of the two plant rows immediately adjacent on either side of the row on which the plants were counted. Row spacing will be recorded on data sheets. Plant density (PD) will be calculated as

$$\text{Plant Density PD} = \text{Average number of plants in 1m} / \text{Average row width in 1m.}$$

3.3.3 Row direction

The direction of planting will be recorded (in degrees) using a compass, and using magnetic North as a reference. Thus, you will need to line up your N direction to the magnetic needle and record the direction of the row based on that reference. Correction of these readings to true North can be done afterwards.

3.3.4 VG4: Plant Area Index & fCover

Plant area index (PAI) can be measured using digital hemispherical photographs. With this technique a wide-angle or fisheye lens captures all sky directions at the same time. When canopies are small, the photos are taken with the lens pointed towards the ground. For tall canopies, the camera is placed on the ground looking skyward. The fisheye photos record the geometry of the plant canopy obstructing the field of view of the soil or sky.

An advantage of this method relative to other in situ approaches (such as the LAI2000) is that the data capture is much less sensitive to sky conditions. Plant canopy analyzers such as the LAI2000 require diffuse sky conditions, restricting data capture to early morning or evening collection or

Figure 3.3: PAI sampling strategy.

collection under consistent overcast conditions. As well, high errors will occur when attempting to capture the LAI of very short vegetation (or early emerging vegetation) as the distance from the lens to the canopy is too small.

PAI will be captured using hemispherical digital photos. Five photos will be taken along two transects (10 photos in total) at each of the sampling sites (Fig. 3.3). These photos will be post processed using the Caneye software to provide an estimate of PAI. In the case of row crops, photos will be taken in the middle of the crop row.

- Take the first photo at sampling location (5m-5m edge).
- Take photos 2-5 at 2 meter increments along first transect.
- Cross over to second row, and take photos 6-10 at 2 meter increments along this second transect.
- When walking back on this second transect, be sure to offset the location of photos as shown in Figure.
- Record the photo numbers on the data sheet.

- R** When taking the photo, the operator should always face the sun.

3.3.5 VG5: Biomass and canopy water content

Vegetation biomass will be collected via destructive sampling. Canopy water content is derived from the biomass samples. One biomass sample will be collected per measurement site.

For cereal crops and grassland, a 0.25 m×0.25 m square will be placed over the canopy. All above ground biomass will be collected by cutting all vegetation at the soil level. This approach is also well suited for crops which are broadcast seeded, or which have very dense planting.

For row crops (e.g. potato, corn and soybeans fields), 5 plants along two rows (10 plants in total) will be collected. Knowledge of the density of the crop will permit scaling of these measurements to a unit area (m²). Any weeds that are collected in the sampling plot are discarded in the field but should be noted on the data sheets if the amount is significant. Photos should also be taken for documentation purposes.

For larger biomass and wide-spaced row crops, biomass will be determined on a per plant basis and scaled to total biomass using the plant density calculations. At each sample location, 10 plants (total) will be harvested from 2 consecutive rows (5 plants×2 rows).

- With a knife, cut the crop at the base of each plant. Do not include residue or weeds in the sample.
- Place the crop in a labeled paper biomass bag. The top of the bag can simply be rolled down. Then place the paper bag inside a plastic bag. Secure the plastic bag with a firm knot.
- The paper bag should be labeled as follows: Field # - Site # Date (Year-Month-Day)
- If the plants are large, it may be necessary to use more than one paper bag. In this case, place each paper bag inside a separate plastic bag and add the following additional label to the paper bag: Sample x of y (for example: Sample 1/3)
- If the plants are wet with dew, gently shake the vegetation prior to bagging.
- Keep the sample with paper bag in hot air oven at 70°C for 3-4days.

Plant water content (PWC) will be calculated as: Plant Water Content (PWC) (g) = (Wet Weight (g) - Plastic Bag Weight (g)) - Dry Weight (g).

For wider spaced row crops (potato, corn, soybeans, sunflower, etc.), plant water content will be scaled to an area basis (grams of water per m²) according to:

[Total PWC (gm) × plant density (per m²)]/Number of plants collected.

Narrow spaced low biomass crops are already collected on an area basis (0.0625 m²). Thus the total plant water content is easily scaled to g/m² by applying a factor of 16.

3.3.6 VG6: Plant height

Crop height can vary significantly and increasing the number of measurements will help to improve the accuracy of the average crop height. Plants that are collected from the biomass sample are used for this measurement. In total, 10 heights will be measured, 5 in each of two rows. For narrow-row crops such as wheat, oats, and barley, the height will be measured to the top of the upper most part of the canopy, whether leaf or fruit. Leaves are to be left in their natural orientation, and not extended, for this measurement. Heights can be measured before or after biomass sampling (whatever is easiest) and recorded on data sheets.

3.3.7 VG7: Plant phenology

The BBCH¹ scale will be used for phenology determination in each sampling location.

3.4 Campaign Schedule

The collection of satellite data and in-situ data took place over a whole vegetation period, starting in early December, where still some fields have been bare and ending in March with the start of the harvesting. The RADARSAT-2 data collection has been done in coordination with the in-situ measurements campaign as shown in Fig. 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Calendar of the Sentinel-2 and RADARSAT-2 data acquisitions along with field campaigns over the test site.

¹Biologische Bundesanstalt, Bundessortenamt und CHemische Industrie—<https://www.politicheagricole.it/flex/AppData/WebLive/Agrometeo/MIEPFY800/BBCHengl2001.pdf>

4. Satellite data acquisitions

4.1 Intensive field campaign period

Table 4.1: Intensive field campaign period.

IOP	Period	Participants	Comment/Data
Campaign 01	08/12/2017–10/12/2017	MRSLab & CA, BCKV	YES
Campaign 02	02/01/2018–04/01/2018	MRSLab & CA, BCKV	YES
Campaign 03	26/01/2018–28/01/2018	MRSLab & CA, BCKV	YES
Campaign 04	18/02/2018–20/02/2018	MRSLab & CA, BCKV	YES
Campaign 05	14/03/2018–16/03/2018	MRSLab & CA, BCKV	YES

4.2 RADARSAT-2 overpasses/acquisition plan

Table 4.2: RADARSAT-2 overpasses/acquisition plan.

Date of acquisition	Orbit	Beam mode	Availability
09/12/2017	Ascending	FQ17	SOAR-EI
02/01/2018	Ascending	FQ17	SOAR-EI
26/01/2018	Ascending	FQ17	SOAR-EI
19/02/2018	Ascending	FQ17	SOAR-EI
15/03/2018	Ascending	FQ17	SOAR-EI

4.3 SENTINEL-1 overpasses/acquisition plan

Refer Table 4.3

Table 4.3: SENTINEL-1 overpasses/acquisition plan.

Date of acquisition	Orbit	Product	Availability in Sci-Hub	Availability in GEE
26/10/2017	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
07/11/2017	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
10/11/2017	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
19/12/2017	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
04/12/2017	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
13/12/2017	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
25/12/2017	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
28/12/2017	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
06/01/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
09/01/2018	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
18/01/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
21/01/2018	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
30/01/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
02/02/2018	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
11/02/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
14/02/2018	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
23/02/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
26/02/2018	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
07/03/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
10/03/2018	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
19/03/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
22/03/2018	Descending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES
31/03/2018	Ascending	SLC+GRD	YES	YES

4.4 SENTINEL-2A/B overpasses/acquisition plan

Refer Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: SENTINEL-2A/B overpasses/acquisition plan.

Date of Acquisition	Platform	Cloud cover	Sci-hub availability	GEE availability
27/09/2017	S2B	Partly	YES	YES
02/10/2017	S2A	YES	YES	YES
17/10/2017	S2B	NO	YES	YES
22/10/2017	S2A	NO	YES	YES
27/10/2017	S2B	NO	YES	YES
06/11/2017	S2B	NO	YES	YES
11/11/2017	S2B	YES	YES	YES
01/12/2017	S2B	NO	YES	YES
21/12/2017	S2B	YES	YES	YES
26/12/2017	S2B	NO	YES	YES
05/01/2018	S2B	Partly	YES	YES
10/01/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
15/01/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
25/01/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
30/01/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
04/02/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
09/02/2018	S2B	YES	YES	YES
14/02/2018	S2B	YES	YES	YES
24/02/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
01/03/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
06/03/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
11/03/2018	S2B	NO	YES	YES
16/03/2018	S2B	YES	YES	YES
21/03/2018	S2A	NO	YES	YES
26/03/2018	S2B	Partly	YES	YES
31/03/2018	S2A	YES	YES	YES

5. Preliminary analysis & results

5.1 Combined Analysis of RADARSAT-2 SAR and Sentinel-2 Optical Data for Improved Monitoring of Tuber Initiation Stage of Potato

5.1.1 Satellite Data and Image Processing

In this study, five RADARSAT-2 fine quad-pol (FQ17) images in single look complex (SLC) format are utilized. All these images were acquired during the intensive observation periods of the field campaign. In a preprocessing step, the covariance matrix $\langle[C]\rangle$ were generated from the scattering matrix of SLC images. Subsequently, the multi-temporal images were speckle filtered using a 3×3 Refined Lee filter and were co-registered. Finally, polarimetric parameters such as backscatter intensities (σ^0), cross-pol ratio HV/VV, linear depolarization ratio $2\sigma_{HV}^0/(\sigma_{HH}^0 + \sigma_{VV}^0)$, and co-pol correlation for each site were calculated as the average of a 3×3 window centred on each site from the elements of the covariance matrix $\langle[C]\rangle$.

Along with the SAR images, twelve Sentinel-2 time series (December 2017- March 2018) images (Level 1C) were acquired over this study area as shown in Figure 5.1.1. Preprocessing steps, e.g. atmospheric corrections (Sen2Cor), spatial resampling to 20m resolution was performed in ESA's Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP) toolbox [9]. Three vegetation indices, i.e. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), and Normalized Difference Index 45 (NDI45) were derived from the pre-processed Sentinel-2 for understanding the spatio-temporal dynamics [10]. Finally, the Vegetation Indices (VIs) for every sampling locations were calculated as the average of a 3 window centred on each location for all dates.

5.1.2 Analysis for early and late plantation of potato

Potato was planted as seed tubers in the majority of fields with a ridge-furrow cultivation system during the 1st-2nd week of December 2017. Upon emergence, plants develop a main-stem with leaves and continue developing leaves in several primary and secondary leaflets up to the inflorescence during the 3rd week after plantation. In a concurrent development process, tuber initiation starts by the formation of tuber beneath the ground and covers the period up to the appearance of the first

flower (in most varieties) to full bloom followed by tuber bulking stage¹. However, as a tuber crop, stolon and tuber initiation provide a distinct developmental stage but are difficult to observe as they occur below the ground. Thus for Earth Observation (EO) data, a proxy of plant growth would be above ground canopy characteristics. A rapid increase in plant leaf area often observed during the tuber initiation stage and ends with peak aboveground biomass accumulation and canopy closure during tuberization. During the tuber bulking stage, plant vegetative growth slows down and the plant growth shifts from vegetative elements to tubers. During senescence, the lower leaves turn yellow and fall from the plant. Subsequently, progressive yellowing of leaves, as well as stems, starts with a decrease in PAI and biomass. The analysis of SAR and optical data with phenological development are separated into two groups. Group-1 includes field no. P03, P11 and P12 as shown in Figure 5.1; and field no. P04, P05 and P13 in Group-2 as shown in Figure 5.2. These groups are solely based on in-situ measurements which indicate that early plantation was practiced in Group-1, whereas Group-2 contains late plantation fields.

Responses to Group-1 (Early plantation) Potato

SAR backscatter responses and VIs for each of the fields throughout the phenological stages are presented in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Observations over the early planted potato fields: temporal behavior of optical NDVI, NDI45, NDWI, radar σ_{HH}^0 , σ_{VV}^0 and σ_{HV}^0 , HV/VV , LDR , ρ_{HH-VV} , and Plant Area Index (PAI), Vegetation water content (VWC) over the test site.

Changes in aboveground biomass (vegetation water content, kgm^{-2}) and Plant Area Index (PAI) within development stages were measured during the field campaigns. The light green rectangular

¹CROPWATCH-<https://cropwatch.unl.edu/potato/tuberization>

box in the PAI/VWC plot represents the tuber initiation stage which occurred during the 1st-3rd week of January 2018 for Group-1 fields. The backscatter intensities (σ_{HH}^0 , σ_{VV}^0 and σ_{HV}^0) decreases as plant canopy grows, which indicates attenuation of C-band signal. The changes in the responses of backscatter ratio parameters and ρ_{HH-VV} are apparent during the tuberization stage. In general, a high correlation between the co-pol channels ($\rho_{HH-VV} \sim 1$) can be observed at the initial growth stage and harvest period of the crop. It is usually characterized by dominating surface scattering from the underlying soil surface. However, the coherence between the co-pol channels drops as the leaf development ends thereby showing an increase in the diffuse scattering component. VIs derived from Sentinel-2 optical data are also in agreement with peak biomass accumulation and PAI for all fields. Conversely, VIs started decreasing after tuberization as plant progressed into tuber bulking.

A distinct difference in responses for field no. P03 is apparent after 19 February 2018. Although, other fields (P11 and P12) were harvested; the P03 field was cultivated with ground pumpkin (*Cucurbita moschata*) which grows laterally after harvest of potato. Thus an increase in VIs is expected from the vegetative growth of pumpkin in P03.

Responses to Group-2 (Late plantation) Potato

As compared to early planted potato fields, the Figure 5.2 represents responses of SAR and optical VIs for comparatively late planted potato. The late plantation of potato is apparent in PAI and biomass plots with the occurrence of peak biomass during the first week of March 2018. The radar backscatter intensities (σ_{HH}^0 , σ_{VV}^0 and σ_{HV}^0) and ratio parameters follows the similar trend. The decrease in co-pol correlation (ρ_{HH-VV}) is evident up to tuberization as canopy closer increased with increase VWC and PAI.

The backscatter intensities (σ_{HH}^0 , σ_{VV}^0 and σ_{HV}^0) decreases as plant canopy grows, which indicates attenuation of C-band signal. The changes in the responses of backscatter ratio parameters and ρ_{HH-VV} are apparent during the tuberization stage. The ρ_{HH-VV} started increasing as crop senescence, indicated similar HH and VV response [11]. VIs derived from Sentinel-2 optical data are also in agreement with peak biomass accumulation and PAI for all fields. Conversely, VIs started decreasing after tuberization as plant progressed into tuber bulking. It is important to note that a sharp decrease in PAI and VWC was observed for field no. P13 during the tuberization stage. It has confirmed from the in-situ measurements that a late blight disease severely affected the field no. P13. This disease affects entire leaflets and stem, and subsequently, a distinctive fatigue was observed in the entire affected field [12]. A sharp decrease in VIs is also apparent due to the late blight diseases over field no. P13.

These findings suggest that combine analysis of SAR observable and optical data derived indices may be able to characterize potato tuberization stage. Monitoring of this critical phenological stage is essential as the yield largely depends on formation and maturity of tubers. This stage also indicates critical agronomic operations, e.g. irrigation and fertilizer (primarily nitrogen group) application. Of note, high humidity and warmer temperature (due to cloudy daytime hours during a winter season) generally acts as a favorable condition of diseases (early and late blight disease) outbreak during the tuberization stages [13]. Thus care should be taken at these critical stages to avoid yield loss.

- R Tuber initiation and tuber bulking stages are critical part of various phenological phases for potato production. Tuber initiation covers the period from the formation of spherical rhizome ends, the flowering and the start of tuber bulking. In general, the tuberization spans from 3 to 5 weeks after emergence and ends with the row closer i.e. canopies in adjacent rows touch each other across the furrow. Hence, this rapid growth seeks critical agronomic management practices such as irrigation and fertilization. It majorly influences the growth of stems, foliar

Figure 5.2: Observations over the late planted potato fields: temporal behavior of optical NDVI, NDI45, NDWI, radar σ_{HH}^0 , σ_{VV}^0 and σ_{HV}^0 , HV/VV , LDR , ρ_{HH-VV} , and Plant Area Index (PAI), Vegetation water content (VWC) over the test site.

area, dry weight and number of tubers particularly at the phase of tuber initiation. During these phenological stages, potato crops are susceptible to the infestation of late blight diseases caused by *Phytophthora infestans* and largely affects the potato production. Thus identifying the crop risk using remote sensing approaches can provide an efficient potato growth monitoring framework [14].

5.2 Acreage estimation for early and late planted potato grown areas using Google's cloud platform

Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data used for estimation of early and late planted areas. A block-wise estimates of acreage was produced in Google Earth Engine (GEE).

The acreage was estimated for the following blocks of Purba Bardhaman district for 2017-2018 growing season (*rabi*):

- Jamalpur
- Raina1
- Raina2
- Burdwan2
- Memari1
- Memari2
- Khandoghosh

Figure 5.3: Spatial variations of plantation delay.

Figure 5.4: Early and late-planted potato sown area (block-wise).

Figure 5.5: Percentage area sown in early and late-plantation (block-wise).

Table 5.1: Acreage (ha.) of early and late-planted potato in different blocks.

Block	Acreage (ha.)	
	Early-planted	Late-planted
Jamalpur	1338.98	9197.15
Raina-I	383.66	2144.36
Raina-II	233.94	1599.25
Burdwan-II	203.50	1107.84
Memari-I	668.80	5966.91
Memari-II	128.17	4930.66
Khandoghosh	625.74	1282.81
Σ	3582.79	26228.98
	$\Sigma = 29811.77$	

Bibliography

- [1] Prashnani M, Singh DK, Joshi R, Ray S. Understanding Crop Growing Pattern in Bardhaman district of West Bengal using Multi-Date RISAT 1 MRS data. *The International Archives of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*. 2014;40(8):861.
- [2] Mandal D, Kumar V, Bhattacharya A, Rao YS, Siqueira P, Bera S. Sen4Rice: A Processing Chain for Differentiating Early and Late Transplanted Rice Using Time-Series Sentinel-1 SAR data with Google Earth Engine. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*. 2018;15(12):1947–1951. DOI: 10.1109/LGRS.2018.2865816.
- [3] Marwaha S R, Singh V S, Pandey K S, Kumar D, Kumar P, Mehta A, et al. Scenario of potato production and processing in West Bengal. Central Potato Research Institute, ICAR; 2007. 85.
- [4] Basu A, Maiti M, et al. Epidemiological study on late blight disease of potato caused by *Phytophthora infestans* in West Bengal. *Journal of Mycopathological Research*. 2007;45(1):90–93.
- [5] Chadha K. *Advances in horticulture*. Malhotra Publ. House; 1993.
- [6] GEOGLAM. JECAM SAR-Inter Comparison Experiment; 2017. Available from: <http://jecam.org/?/jecam-blog/sar-inter-comparison-experiment>.
- [7] McNairn H, Tom J J, Powers J, Bélair S, Berg A, Bullock P, et al.. Experimental Plan SMAP Validation Experiment 2016 in Manitoba, Canada (SMAPVEX16-MB); 2016. Available from: https://smap.jpl.nasa.gov/internal_resources/390/.
- [8] Bhuiyan HA, McNairn H, Powers J, Friesen M, Pacheco A, Jackson TJ, et al. Assessing SMAP Soil Moisture Scaling and Retrieval in the Carman (Canada) Study Site. *Vadose Zone Journal*. 2018;17(1). Doi: 10.2136/vzj2018.07.0132.
- [9] ESA. Sentinel-2 Toolbox - ESA Sentinel; 2014. Available from: <https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/toolboxes/sentinel-2>.

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- [10] Frampton WJ, Dash J, Watmough G, Milton EJ. Evaluating the capabilities of Sentinel-2 for quantitative estimation of biophysical variables in vegetation. *ISPRS journal of photogrammetry and remote sensing*. 2013;82:83–92.
- [11] Hariharan S, Mandal D, Tirodkar S, Kumar V, Bhattacharya A, Lopez-Sanchez JM. A Novel Phenology Based Feature Subset Selection Technique Using Random Forest for Multitemporal PolSAR Crop Classification. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*. 2018;11(11):4244 – 4258. DOI: 10.1109/JSTARS.2018.2866407.
- [12] Arora R, Sharma S, Singh B. Late blight disease of potato and its management. *Potato Journal*. 2014;41(1).
- [13] Hide G, Lapwood D. Disease aspects of potato production. In: *The Potato Crop*. Springer; 1992. p. 403–437.
- [14] Mandal D, Kumar V, Rao Y, Bhattacharya A, Bera S, Nanda MK. Combined Analysis of RADARSAT-2 SAR and Sentinel-2 Optical Data for Improved Monitoring of Tuber Initiation Stage of Potato. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing & Spatial Information Sciences*. 2018;XLII(5):275–279. Doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-5-275-2018.